

Prompting vs. Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning: A Controlled Study of Conversational Efficiency in Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct

Kayra Özdemir

Andrei Osoianu

Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam

Abstract. This paper studies how adaptation strategy, prompting versus parameter-efficient fine-tuning (PEFT), affects the conversational efficiency of small language models in task-oriented dialogue. Using the Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct model, a controlled hotel recommendation task with simulated user and assistant agents is evaluated. The assistant is tested across prompt-based and PEFT variants, two user personas, and with or without long-term memory, yielding eight experimental configurations. Performance is measured using objective interaction metrics and subjective quality judgments from an independent LLM-based evaluator, supported by manual analysis. Results show that prompt-based adaptation consistently outperforms PEFT in efficiency, groundedness, and overall quality, while user persona strongly shapes dialogue behavior. Long-term memory provides modest coherence benefits but does not substantially improve factual grounding.

Keywords: Conversational AI · LLMs · In-Context Learning · Fine-tuning · PEFT · Long-term Memory · Retrieval · Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

When it comes to task-oriented dialog systems [1], adapting a general-purpose LLM typically requires a decision between prompt tuning (in-context learning) and fine-tuning [2], [3]. Even though prompting is based on zero-shot instructions [4], [5], Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) [6], [5], which is achieved by techniques such as Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) [7], [8], is a more resource-free approach compared to Full Fine-Tuning, which updates only a subset of the model parameters for adapting it to domain-specific behaviors. Finally, to make these systems more dependable, it is common nowadays to incorporate Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) [9].

1.2 Aim of This Paper

The main aim of the research is to assess how adaptation strategies affect the performance of small LLMs in a task-related setting [1]. More concretely, in the

present work, the Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct LLM [10] will be analyzed in terms of whether the computational cost of fine-tuning brings additional benefits over in-context learning [2], [3]. Indeed, the research will tackle the following research question: **To what extent can adaptation strategy, in terms of Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning [5], [6] vs. Prompting [4], affect the conversational efficiency of the Qwen2.5-1.5B LLM in a controlled task-related dialog?**

2 Methodology

2.1 Task

The task considered in this work is a controlled hotel recommendation dialogue between a simulated assistant agent and a simulated user agent. The assistant’s objective is to recommend suitable hotels from a fixed dataset based on the user’s preferences, which are revealed incrementally over multiple turns. The user refines constraints such as budget, location, and amenities through interaction [1].

2.2 Synthetic Data Generation

A fully synthetic hotel dataset is generated programmatically to ensure reproducibility, experimental control, and independence from external data sources [11], [12]. Each hotel follows a fixed schema. Hotel names are constructed via adjective-noun composition with enforced global uniqueness to avoid entity collisions. Review snippets are sampled from predefined semantic topics (e.g., location, staff, cleanliness, noise, amenities) to simulate multi-aspect feedback, with explicit constraints preventing duplicate snippets within the same hotel. Numerical ratings are computed using a sentiment-aware heuristic that aligns textual reviews with numeric scores [13]. Amenities, neighborhoods, and distances are sampled from bounded pools to reflect realistic urban variation. All generation steps are stochastic but constrained, balancing diversity with internal consistency. The dataset size is intentionally limited ($N = 100$) to match the experimental scale and avoid dominance effects during retrieval and dialogue generation.

Topic Balancing and Review Sampling. Topic coverage is controlled through a fixed categorical distribution, and cross-hotel duplication is reduced using a global usage-weighted sampler that favors less frequently used snippets [11], [14].

$$t \sim \text{Categorical}(\{p_t\}_{t \in \mathcal{T}}), \quad \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} p_t = 1$$

$$w_t(r) = \frac{1}{1 + u_t(r)}, \quad \pi_t(r) = \frac{w_t(r)}{\sum_{r' \in C_t} w_t(r')} \quad u_t(r) \leftarrow u_t(r) + 1$$

Within each hotel h , snippet reuse is prevented by enforcing $r_k \notin U_h$, with a fallback reset if candidates are exhausted. *Notation:* \mathcal{T} denotes the set of review topics; p_t the sampling probability of topic t ; r a candidate review snippet; $u_t(r)$ its global usage count; C_t the snippet pool for topic t .

Rating Alignment. Ratings are initialized from a bounded uniform distribution and adjusted according to sentiment cues in the sampled reviews [13]-[15].

$$R_0 \sim \text{Uniform}(3.0, 5.0), \quad R = R_0 + \sum_{s \in S_h} \Delta(s) \quad \text{rating} = \text{round}(\text{clip}(R, 2.8, 5.0), 1)$$

Notation: R_0 is the base rating; S_h the set of review snippets for hotel h ; $\Delta(s)$ a sentiment-based adjustment derived from snippet s .

Table 1: Synthetic Hotel Dataset Schema

Field	Description
id	Unique hotel identifier
name	Generated hotel name (adjective-noun composition)
location	City name (fixed to Amsterdam)
neighborhood	Urban neighborhood label
distance_to_center_km	Distance to city center (km)
rating	Numerical rating (2.8-5.0)
price	Price category (\$, \$\$, \$\$\$)
price_numeric	Numeric price level (1-3)
amenities	List of available amenities
review_snippets	2-6 short textual review statements

2.3 Agents

Assistant Agent. The assistant agent is instantiated from Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct [10] and is responsible for generating hotel recommendations based on the ongoing dialogue context. All assistant variants share the same base model and architecture, differing only in their adaptation strategy (prompt-based [4] or parameter-efficient fine-tuning [5], [6]). The assistant does not perform independent retrieval or reasoning beyond the candidate hotels provided by the retrieval module.

Prompt. The prompt-based assistant variant is governed entirely by a fixed system prompt that specifies behavioral constraints, hallucination avoidance rules, dialogue conduct, and the overall task objective [4].

User Agent. The user agent is also instantiated from Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct [10] and the user agent is responsible for generating questions for the assistant agent to answer. Rather than issuing complete task specifications upfront, the user expresses preferences incrementally in response to assistant suggestions. User utterances are generated based on the dialogue history, and a fixed persona prompt. The user agent does not explicitly evaluate the assistant but drives the dialogue forward until termination conditions are met [1], [4].

Personas. There are two persona prompts used only for the user agent for variability. The first persona is characterized by a minimalist user trying to get the assistant to fulfill requests and answer questions concisely. The second persona is characterized by an explorer user evaluating the many options and having a more sincere conversation [4].

2.4 LoRA Training

Training Dataset. The fine-tuning dataset is constructed from dialogues generated by the prompt-based assistant variant with long-term memory activated, which serves as a teacher model [11], [12]. Conversations are collected under both user personas (minimalist and explorer), and merged into a single training corpus. Each dialogue is decomposed into multiple supervised examples by iterating over assistant turns. For every assistant response, the preceding dialogue history is linearized into a structured transcript consisting of system instructions, alternating user and assistant turns, and a final assistant generation prompt. The corresponding ground-truth output is the assistant’s original reply at that turn [1].

Balancing. To prevent persona imbalance, training examples are grouped by persona and downsampled to the smallest persona subset. 107 examples were available for the minimalist persona and 79 for the explorer persona; both were capped at 79 examples, yielding a balanced dataset of 158 total training instances.

Table 2: Training Dataset Balancing across User Personas

Persona	Number of Examples
Minimalist (before)	107
Explorer (before)	79
Balanced per persona	79
Total training examples	158

Setup. Parameter-efficient fine-tuning is implemented using Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA), applied to the Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct [10] base model. LoRA adapters are inserted into the attention projection layers (`q_proj`, `k_proj`, `v_proj`, `o_proj`) with rank $r = 8$, scaling factor $\alpha = 16$, and dropout of 0.05. All base model parameters remain frozen, and only the adapter weights are updated during training. The LoRA adapters were trained for 3 epochs using AdamW with a learning rate of 2×10^{-4} , linear warmup (3%), an effective batch size of 16 (batch size 2 with gradient accumulation of 8), and a maximum sequence length of 512 tokens [7], [8]. This results in approximately 0.14% of the total parameters being trainable, significantly reducing memory and compute requirements. A higher learning rate is used for adapter training compared to full fine-tuning, following standard PEFT practice [5], [6]. This setup was selected due to computational constraints and to enable controlled comparison against prompt-based adaptation, and the limitations of this choice are discussed in Section 7.

```

trainable params: 2,179,072
all params: 1,545,893,376
trainable%: 0.1410

```

Fig. 1: Parameter Footprint of LoRA for Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct.

2.5 Long-term Memory

User Profiler Agent. A user profiler agent is employed to maintain long-term user preferences across multiple dialogue sessions. After a conversation terminates with user satisfaction, the full dialogue history is summarized by an LLM into a structured user profile [16], [17]. The profiler utilizes the Qwen2.5-1.5B-Instruct [10] model with low temperature (0.1) to ensure consistent extraction of user traits from dialogue history. The profiler extracts 24 structured preference fields from dialogue history using a strict JSON schema with regex-based fallback parsing. This regex-based fallback parser is employed to ensure robustness against malformed or partially structured LLM outputs. Afterwards, these schemas are used to summarize details for prompt injection [18].

Table 3: User Profiler JSON Schema (Grouped)

Field Group	Fields and Description
Identity	<code>trip_type</code> (business/romantic/leisure/unknown), <code>persona_name</code> (assigned persona)
Budget	<code>budget_min</code> , <code>budget_max</code> (numeric bounds), <code>currency</code> (string/null)
Location Preference	<code>wants_central_location</code> <code>wants_local_neighborhood</code> (true/false/null)
Atmosphere Preference	<code>prefers_quiet</code> , <code>prefers_social</code> (true/false/null)
Amenity Priorities	<code>cares_about_wifi</code> , <code>desk</code> , <code>breakfast</code> , <code>parking</code> , <code>gym</code> , <code>rooftop</code> , <code>spa</code> (true/false/null)
Lifestyle Signals	<code>foodie</code> , <code>romantic</code> (true/false/null)
Explicit Feedback	<code>preferred_hotels</code> , <code>rejected_hotels</code> (array of strings or empty list)
Free-form Memory	<code>free_form_notes</code> (unstructured string)

Memory. Long-term memory is implemented as a lightweight state module that separates session-level dialogue history from persistent cross-session context, inspired by Mem0 [19]. During each conversation, the module stores a turn-by-turn record of user and assistant utterances, indexed by a unique session identifier and used only for in-session tracking and after-the-session profiling. Persistent memory is stored independently as a compact textual summary of accumulated user preferences and is written only after a session terminates, avoiding interference from partial or unstable signals. When available, long-term

memory is injected into the assistant’s system prompt as a bounded bullet-point context block [20], [18].

Profile Post-processing. After each batch of conversations, user profiles undergo a small post-processing step to remove redundant free-form content introduced by forced dialogue closure. Specifically, free-form notes containing generic gratitude or closing compliments (e.g., “thank you”, “great recommendation”) are automatically cleared, as these signals do not reflect stable user preferences. This post-processing prevents the long-term memory from accumulating conversational noise while preserving meaningful preference information.

2.6 Dialogue Setup

Retrieval. Hotel data retrieval is implemented via a lightweight, deterministic retrieval module operating over a fixed synthetic dataset. For each assistant turn, a subset of candidate hotels is selected by filtering on location and optionally rating or price constraints. Candidates are sorted by descending rating and ascending price before being truncated to a fixed limit ($N = 5$). The retrieval module does not perform embedding-based search, re-ranking, or query rewriting, and there is no inherent RAG module. Retrieved hotel entries are passed unchanged to the assistant as structured context [14], [9].

Similarity-Based Termination Control. To guide dialogue closure, a similarity-based repetition control mechanism is applied during the conversation. Assistant responses are compared against earlier assistant turns using BERTScore to detect semantic repetition. User responses are compared against earlier user turns using earlier user turns, again via BERTScore, to detect semantic similarity, and therefore repetition. The earlier turns concern all of that dialogue’s history. Furthermore, the user agent’s response is also compared to a pre-defined set of assistant-like outputs, to deny the user agent from roleplaying as the assistant. When similarity exceeds a predefined threshold of 92%, the system automatically tries again with a higher temperature, and otherwise a fallback interaction toward termination is utilized [21].

Satisfaction Judge Agent. A separate LLM-based satisfaction judge agent is used to determine whether a dialogue should terminate. The judge receives the full dialogue history and evaluates whether the user’s request has been sufficiently addressed, answering a "YES" or "NO" strictly. This answer is then directly encoded into a binary satisfaction signal by checking whether the first character of the generated output contains the letter Y, therefore denoting a boolean True. Otherwise the signal is converted into a boolean False in any other case. The judge does not influence response generation and is only queried after user turns [17], [16].

2.7 Pipeline

The overall system follows a modular, sequential pipeline. The user agent and assistant agent interact turn by turn. At each assistant turn, candidate hotels

Fig. 2: Semantic Repetition Detection and Termination Control.

Fig. 3: End-to-end Dialogue Pipeline.

are retrieved from the synthetic dataset and injected into the assistant’s prompt. Dialogue termination is governed by similarity-based repetition control and an external satisfaction judge. After termination, the full dialogue is passed to a user profiler to update long-term memory, which is persisted across sessions and reused in subsequent interactions.

3 Experimental Setup

3.1 Agent Variants

A full factorial experimental design was utilized to isolate the specific contributions of the adaptation strategy and memory availability. This results in a total setup of $2 \times 2 \times 2 = 8$ distinct configurations:

- **Assistant (2 levels):** The baseline *Prompt-Based* assistant against the fine-tuned *PEFT (LoRA)* assistant.

- **User Persona (2 levels):** Both *Minimalist* and *Explorer* user personas to check for behavioral consistency.
- **Memory Condition (2 levels):** A *Memory-Free* baseline against a *Long-Term Memory* condition.

3.2 Memory Conditions

Each assistant agent is started with a fixed memory seed, ensuring they have the same information present at start. This memory seed was attained from the baseline-prompt model with long-term memory on both user personas.

3.3 Dialogue Seeding

Conversations are not started randomly. Instead, a dataset of **20 fixed dialogue seeds** (Initial Histories) is utilized. Each seed consists of a single initial user turn that sets the goal for the conversation. Every agent pair runs through the exact same sequence of 20 seeds to ensure experiment conditions that are fully aligned between all agent configurations:

- **Minimalist Seeds ($N = 10$):** Prompts focusing more on hard constraints and utility.
- **Explorer Seeds ($N = 10$):** Prompts focusing more on atmosphere and qualitative experience.

3.4 Evaluation Protocol

Conversational performance is evaluated using a combination of objective interaction metrics and subjective quality judgments, reflecting both behavioral efficiency and response quality under controlled dialogue conditions.

Objective Metrics. Objective metrics include (i) conversation length, measured by average number of turns and (ii) token-level efficiency, including assistant tokens per turn, and assistant-to-user token ratio. A binary success signal derived from enforced termination (`user_satisfied`) is retained for completeness but is not used as a discriminative metric, as closure is systematically enforced. Objective metrics are aggregated per experimental condition and reported as mean values across conversations [22]. These metrics were selected to capture aspects of conversational efficiency: dialogue length reflects task convergence speed, and token-based measures capture verbosity and information density.

Subjective Metrics. Subjective evaluation is performed by an independent LLM-based judge [17], [16] using the Qwen2.5-**3B**-Instruct model [10] that assesses full dialogue transcripts along multiple qualitative dimensions. The judge assigns Likert-scale scores between 1-5 for the dimensions: task fulfillment, groundedness, clarity, pleasantness, and overall quality; and additionally outputs a binary success judgment and a short textual justification. The judge is explicitly instructed to penalize unsupported claims, speculative reasoning, and invented facts, and to avoid rewarding verbosity. Subjective evaluation thus complements objective metrics by capturing aspects of conversational quality that are not observable through surface-level statistics [15].

4 Results

Fig. 4: Objective efficiency metrics: Assistant tokens per turn across model variants, personas, and memory conditions (a-c); Assistant-to-user token ratio (d-f); Average dialogue length in turns. (g-i)

Fig. 5: Subjective evaluation: overall quality ratings from independent judge (left), detailed subjective scores across dimensions (right).

5 Analysis

5.1 Objective Metrics

Assistant Variants Comparison. Across all conditions, the PEFT assistant produces shorter responses per turn on average than the prompt-based assistant, indicating that fine-tuning internalizes task constraints more compactly than explicit prompting. In contrast, the prompt-based assistant consistently exhibits a higher assistant–user token ratio, reflecting more verbose and explanatory behavior. Despite this increased verbosity, prompt-based dialogues terminate in fewer turns overall. This suggests that front-loading information through longer responses compensates for the lack of internalized task structure, whereas PEFT assistants distribute decision-making over a larger number of shorter turns.

User Personas Comparison. The user persona significantly influences both the verbosity and conversation flow of the assistant. In this way, the responses of minimalist user personas are shorter, specifically for the PEFT assistant, whereas those of explorer user personas are longer and informative, thus validating the fact that persona cues do affect the assistant effectively. On the assistant-user ratio, there are higher ratios in the case of user personas exploring, thus implying that even the shortest user input prompts relatively heavier responses, specifically in adaptive scenarios. On dialogue length, explorer dialogue turns are significantly lower in numbers than in the case of user personas acting as minimalists.

Effect of Long-Term Memory. Enabling long-term memory results in a small, constant boost in the number of assistant tokens per turn, which is likely driven by the fact that answers involve user preferences stored in memory rather than being rebuilt turn by turn. Nevertheless, the effect on the ratio of assistant to user tokens is negligible, and thus the dialog balance is still sustained. Furthermore, the number of turns itself decreases by a tiny amount in memory-enabled dialogues, which indicates that long-term user context helps to converge on a recommendation faster, even if the average response size is slightly increased.

5.2 Subjective Evaluation

Overall. Across all conditions, subjective scores remain high, indicating that both adaptation strategies produce acceptable dialogue behavior. Prompt-based assistants consistently achieve slightly higher overall quality than PEFT variants. Explorer personas are rated higher than minimalist personas, while long-term memory yields a small but consistent improvement across both assistant variants.

By Metric. Task fulfillment and clarity are the strongest dimensions overall, with prompt-based assistants outperforming PEFT under both personas. Groundedness is the weakest metric across conditions and shows minimal sensitivity to memory, but is consistently higher for prompt-based assistants. Pleasantness is primarily driven by user persona: explorer dialogues score higher regardless of assistant variant or memory condition. Long-term memory produces modest gains in clarity and overall quality, but has negligible impact on groundedness or task fulfillment.

5.3 Manual Evaluation & Discussion

To complement the automatic subjective evaluation, a manual inspection of a stratified sample of conversations across all experimental conditions was conducted. For each combination of configurations, five complete dialogues were reviewed. The analysis follows the same four dimensions (excluding overall quality, replaced by alignment with humans) used by the LLM judge [15], [16].

Task Fulfilment. Task fulfillment is consistently high across all conditions, as both assistant variants reliably provide hotel recommendations aligned with user constraints and continue until explicit user satisfaction. Prompt-based assistants adapt more effectively to follow-up questions, particularly for explorer personas, whereas PEFT assistants occasionally fall back on repetitive high-level descriptions, slightly reducing perceived completeness.

Groundedness. Groundedness remains the weakest dimension overall. PEFT assistants frequently introduce plausible but unsupported details (e.g., restaurants, events, transport), while prompt-based assistants more often acknowledge uncertainty, resulting in higher groundedness scores. Long-term memory has little effect on groundedness, indicating that repetition control does not mitigate hallucinated content.

Clarity. Clarity scores are uniformly high. Responses are generally well-structured and easy to follow, with prompt-based assistants producing more concise and focused answers, especially for minimalist personas. Long-term memory provides a small clarity benefit by reducing redundancy in longer explorer dialogues.

Pleasantness. Pleasantness is primarily driven by user persona rather than assistant variant. Explorer dialogues are more engaging and expressive, leading to higher pleasantness scores, while minimalist dialogues are more transactional by design. Prompt-based assistants slightly outperform PEFT models by better matching the user’s communicative style.

Alignment with Human Evaluation. Overall, the LLM-Judge aligned well with human judgement based on the smaller subset of 5 dialogues per variant (roughly 35 out of 40 conversations aligned well), sometimes missing some hallucination cases or being afraid to give too extreme scores, most likely due to the scale compression effect or central tendency bias [23], [24].

6 Conclusion

This paper investigated how adaptation strategy-prompting versus parameter-efficient fine-tuning affects the conversational efficiency of a small instruction-tuned language model in a controlled task-oriented dialogue setting. Overall, **prompt-based adaptation consistently outperforms PEFT** in conversational quality and efficiency. Prompt-based assistants terminate dialogues in fewer turns, exhibit higher groundedness, and adapt more effectively to follow-up questions, particularly for explorer personas. PEFT assistants, while parameter-efficient, tend to spread decision-making over more turns and show higher levels of repetition or unsupported detail, which weakens perceived groundedness despite successful task completion. User persona strongly influences dialogue dynamics: explorer personas yield more expressive, pleasant interactions, whereas minimalist personas produce denser but more compact exchanges. Long-term memory provides modest benefits by reducing repetition and slightly accelerating convergence, but does not meaningfully improve factual grounding. Taken together, while PEFT was expected to improve efficiency by internalizing task constraints, the results indicate that for small LLMs in constrained task-oriented settings, **carefully designed prompting remains a more reliable and effective adaptation strategy than lightweight fine-tuning.**

7 Future Work & Limitations

This study was limited due to computational power: small model, synthetic data, and short simulated dialogues. Future work should explore larger models, longer and more diverse conversations, improved evaluation metrics, full fine-tuning, better termination conditions, and the integration of retrieval-augmented generation to strengthen grounding.

A Appendix

Fig. 6: Additional objective metrics for lexical diversity, calculated by type-token ratio over assistant-generated text only.

Fig. 7: Additional satisfaction metrics and the overall performance of the satisfaction judge (right).

Fig. 8: Trade-off between conversational efficiency (tokens per turn) and lexical diversity across experimental conditions. Points represent individual conversations, colored by assistant variant.

GENERAL BEHAVIOR: Base suggestions ONLY on provided hotel candidates and internal reviews. Do NOT quote, paraphrase, or reference review text. Express only high-level properties in your own words. NEVER invent hotels or real-world facts.

NO HALLUCINATIONS: If a detail is unknown, explicitly state this. Do NOT speculate or invent amenities or named locations.

DIALOGUE CONDUCT: Ask clarifying questions when constraints are unclear. Compare 2-3 hotels concisely. End each response with ONE best option. Write ONLY the assistant's reply.

PERSONA_MINIMALIST:

- You are efficient, pragmatic, and dislike small talk.
- You value time and want a hotel that fits your constraints quickly.
- You ask a few clear questions and then decide.
- You prefer concise, factual answers rather than long explanations.

PERSONA_EXPLORER:

- You are curious and high in openness.
- You care a lot about atmosphere, uniqueness, and local experiences.
- You tend to ask several follow-up questions about ambiance, neighborhood, and special features.
- You may consider multiple options before deciding and enjoy a bit of conversation.

Fig. 9: System prompt given to assistant agent across all variations (top), user agent persona prompts (bottom)

GitHub Repository. All of the experimentation & architecture code can be found online in the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/thewyveo/dual-LLM-dialogue/>

Statement of Contribution.

- **Author K. Özdemir:** All of the code (including synthetic data generation), revision of introduction section, all of the methodology section, revision of experimental setup, 3.4 evaluation protocol, all of the results section, all of the analysis section, all of the conclusion section, all of the future work & limitations section, all of the appendix, abstract, keywords, title, styling, figures, GitHub repository.
- **Author A. Osoianu:** Introduction section, experimental setup section (excluding 3.4 evaluation protocol), manual evaluation process, helped with future work/limitations.

Statement of Use of Generative AI. Generative AI tools were used to support the development of this work, primarily for clarification of technical explanations, assistance with code debugging and visualization design (figures, TikZ library artifacts

in LaTeX, etc.). All experimental design decisions, data generation, implementation, evaluation, and interpretation of results were conducted by the authors.

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1. All experiments were conducted using PyTorch and HuggingFace Transformers on a single GPU-enabled workstation (namely, a Macbook Pro with an M4 chip).
2. The full fine-tuning code was fully developed with a dataset builder, training loop, and the `AssistantAgentFT` class was designed to accept both full-FT and PEFT. However due to computational limits this approach could not be explored.
3. Initial design worked by adding the conversations to the dataset at the end of each dialogue, rather than each session. This resulted in the artifact that earlier conversations were kept in the dataset. This file was not used as the final results file in the end result, however it was used as the training data, and therefore balancing needed to be done. This is most likely why the training dataset ended up with extra examples for the minimalist persona.
4. Some additional objective metrics were computed, however not discussed. The reason they were discarded is either because they weren't informative, or because they didn't fit in. These are provided in the appendix.

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